

FREQUENCY DOMAIN FATIGUE APPROACH FOR SINE SWEEP LOADINGS

G. de Moraes

Many automotive manufacturers do not have accurate fatigue loading data for the mechanical components they build. In such cases the solution is to design in compliance with particular guidelines or rely on simplified tests that are able to cover the worst case scenarios. The Sine Sweep Vibration Test is one of those simplified tests that can be used to obtain relevant modal parameters and/or evaluate structural integrity. The design of reliable sine sweep tests depends on the accuracy of the finite element analysis and the fatigue approach used in the design process. The time domain approach is the most commonly used for fatigue analysis (*partially due to its simplicity*) but it is computationally expensive. This paper brings the frequency domain approach as the most viable alternative to evaluating a sine sweep fatigue analysis from finite element results. It will be shown that sweep type, duration and damping are the most important parameters to be observed in order to keep the error (*difference between time and frequency domain*) under 10%. It was found that the error decreases the larger the damping and sweep duration.

Keywords: Metal fatigue, Vibration, Sine-Sweep, Frequency Domain

INTRODUCTION

The experiments conducted to determine if a component or a system meet specific standards or requirements are called qualification tests. They are designed to ensure the subjects being tested are fit for purpose and comply with performance requirements, safety assurances and reliability criteria. Examples of qualification tests are found in guidelines like MIL-STD-810F, ECSS-E-10-03C and PK, Braccesi et al. [1]. The most commonly employed qualification tests are the random vibration, sine-on-random and sine-sweep. The application of any of them will depend on the components being evaluated and their function, but the sine-sweep stands out (among the three) as it can also be used to deduce the dynamic characteristics (e.g. the resonant frequencies and damping) of the tested specimen based on the measured responses as well as being used for fatigue life qualification.

The essence of a sine sweep test is that the base excitation input consists of a single frequency at any given time, where the frequency itself, however, varies with time. It may begin at a low frequency and then sweep to a high frequency (or swing back and forth), while the specified excitation amplitude varies with frequency (Figure 1). Ideally, the sweep rate would be sufficiently low to enable the response of the component to reach a high percentage of the level obtained in steady

SIMULIA Technology Manager Senior Specialist, Dassault Systemes, UK.

operation under pure sinusoidal excitation. Therefore, the swept sine can be understood as a logical extension of the sinusoidal vibration at constant frequency (*aka dwell test*).

FIGURE 1 Sine Sweep Specification Example.

Linear and Logarithmic sweeps are the most common options. The formula for the excitation amplitude, $Y(t)$, in a linear sine sweep is given by Irvine [2]:

$$Y(t) = A \cdot \sin\left(2\pi\left(f_{min}t + \frac{R}{2}t^2\right)\right) \tag{1}$$

and the linear sweep rate R is defined as

$$R = \frac{f_{max} - f_{min}}{T} \tag{2}$$

A is the amplitude scale, f_{min} is the starting frequency, f_{max} is the ending frequency, t is the elapsed time and T the duration (total time). Figure 2 below is an example of a constant amplitude swept sinusoidal representation in the time domain.

FIGURE 2 Sine Sweep load represented in the time domain.

The formula for the amplitudes in a logarithmic sweep is given by Irvine [2]:

$$Y(t) = A \cdot \sin\left(2\pi\left(\frac{f_0(-1+2^{Rt})}{R\ln(2)t}\right)t\right) \tag{3}$$

where the sweep rate R is defined as

$$R = \frac{N_{oct}}{T} \quad (4)$$

and N_{oct} is the number of octaves per time and T is the duration.

$$N_{oct} = \frac{\ln(f_2/f_1)}{\ln(2)} \quad (5)$$

In other words, an octave is the interval between two frequencies whose ratio is 2

$$\frac{f_2}{f_1} = 2^{N_{oct}} \quad (6)$$

STRUCTURAL LINEAR DYNAMICS

A fair amount of vibration problems, especially in the automotive industry, can be approached successfully by linear dynamics, Maymon [3]. Linear dynamics can be handled in the time or frequency domain, where the choice for one or another will depend on the nature of the loads, i.e., whether it is periodic, quasi-periodic or non-periodic. The frequency domain is indicated for the first two processes, but not for the third. Solving a linear dynamics problem involves the evaluation of the following equation of motion:

$$[M]\{\ddot{z}\} + [C]\{\dot{z}\} + [K]\{z\} = \{F\} \quad (7)$$

where $[M]$, $[C]$, $[K]$ are the mass, damping and stiffness matrices, $\{F\}$ is the force vector, $\{z\}$, $\{\dot{z}\}$ and $\{\ddot{z}\}$ are the displacement, velocity and acceleration vectors. Equation 7 can not be solved by hand when the geometry is complex, hence the Finite Element Method (*FEM*) is used instead. Equation 7 is actually a system of equations. When they are not significantly coupled by damping the normal modes can be used to make the system diagonal; separating the freedoms so that they can be treated as a series of single degrees of freedom and therefore much easier to solve, Thorby [4]. Eigenanalysis is the name of the linear algebra transformation required to get the normal modes, here represented by $[X]$. They allow the matrices in Equation 7 to be represented in modal coordinates as

$$[\underline{M}] = [X]^T [M] [X] \quad (8)$$

$$[\underline{C}] = [X]^T [C] [X] \quad (9)$$

$$[\underline{K}] = [X]^T [K] [X] \quad (10)$$

$$\{Q\} = [X]^T \{F\} \quad (11)$$

where $[\underline{M}]$ represents the generalized or modal masses, $[\underline{C}]$ is the generalized or modal damping, $[\underline{K}]$ is the generalized or modal stiffness and $\{Q\}$ the generalized modal forces. Finally Equation 7 can be re-written as

$$[\underline{M}]\{\ddot{q}\} + [\underline{C}]\{\dot{q}\} + [\underline{K}]\{q\} = \{Q\} \quad (12)$$

and the modal coordinates $\{q\}$ are obtained. The modal coordinates (as the name suggests) transform the results in the modal coordinates back to global coordinates. Take the stresses for example:

$$\{\sigma\} = [X_s]\{q\} \quad (13)$$

where $[X_s]$ represents the modal stresses, which are obtained from the modal analysis (or frequency extraction) when FEM is employed. Then the modal coordinates $\{q\}$ are obtained by the subsequent harmonic analysis (aka steady state dynamic analysis). The technique used to solve the equation of motion (7) using normal modes is denominated modal superposition (MSUP). The number of modes to include in a modal dynamic analysis varies from case to case, Morais [5].

THE DYNAMIC ANALYSIS WORKFLOW

The modal coordinates obtained from the harmonic analysis are basically a set of complex scale factors (also called generalized displacements) that multiply the modal stresses so that a frequency response function can be evaluated.

For each frequency f we have a vector $\mathbf{u}(f)$ of generalized displacements over the K modes:

$$\mathbf{u}(f) = (u_1(f), u_2(f), \dots, u_K(f))^T \quad (14)$$

For each material point (element-node) we also have a set of modal stress tensors $\{\mathbf{m}_1, \mathbf{m}_2, \dots, \mathbf{m}_K\}$, represented as 6-vectors, which can be written as a matrix $\mathbf{M}$, whose columns are the modal stress tensor for the corresponding mode, so

$$\mathbf{M} = (\mathbf{m}_1 | \mathbf{m}_2 | \dots | \mathbf{m}_K) \quad (15)$$

with $\mathbf{m}_i = (m_{i,xx}, m_{i,yy}, m_{i,zz}, m_{i,xy}, m_{i,yz}, m_{i,xz})^T$

Given a sweep profile function $p(f)$ defining the sweep acceleration amplitudes at each frequency in the range of the sweep, the sweep response over frequency can be computed by multiplying the generalised displacement vector by the modal stress matrix and weighting by the sweep profile. Hence at each frequency f we have a response tensor $\sigma_a(f)$ representing the response amplitude along the different component directions,

$$\sigma_a(f) = (\sigma_{xx,a}, \sigma_{yy,a}, \sigma_{zz,a}, \sigma_{xy,a}, \sigma_{yz,a}, \sigma_{xz,a})^T \quad (16)$$

computed as:

$$\sigma_a(f) = p(f)\mathbf{M}(f)\mathbf{u}(f) \quad (17)$$

Note that this represents amplitudes, not raw stress values, and is complex. From this point the two options for the multiaxial reduction are the Critical Plane (CP) and Von Mises approaches. The Von Mises approach must account for the fact that the response is complex (including phasing information), so the usual quadratic terms in the Von Mises expression are replaced by multiplying each term by its complex conjugate. We drop the frequency variable for ease of notation, but the following is computed at each frequency.

Consider first the non-shear contribution to the Von Mises stress, Preumont [6].

Define the 3-vector of their differences $\mathbf{s}_\Delta = (\sigma_{xx,a} - \sigma_{yy,a}, \sigma_{yy,a} - \sigma_{zz,a}, \sigma_{xx,a} - \sigma_{zz,a})^T$ and its conjugate (Hermitian) transpose as $\mathbf{s}_\Delta^H$. Then the Von Mises response amplitude is given by

$$\sigma_{vm,a} = \sqrt{\frac{\mathbf{s}_\Delta \mathbf{s}_\Delta^H}{2} + 3(\sigma_{xy,a} \sigma_{xy,a}^* + \sigma_{yz,a} \sigma_{yz,a}^* + \sigma_{xz,a} \sigma_{xz,a}^*)} \quad (18)$$

The *CP* Approach requires the determination of the plane normal and a shear direction so that normal and shear projections can take place, Socie et al. [7]:

$$\sigma_{n,a}(f) = \mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{n}^T \quad (19)$$

$$\tau_a(f) = \mathbf{t} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{n}^T \quad (20)$$

Where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is defined as:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{xx,a}(f) & \sigma_{xy,a}(f) & \sigma_{xz,a}(f) \\ & \sigma_{yy,a}(f) & \sigma_{yz,a}(f) \\ & & \sigma_{zz,a}(f) \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

Then the equivalent shear stress function can be evaluated:

$$\tau_{eq,a}(f) = \tau_a(f) + k \cdot \sigma_{n,a}(f) \quad (22)$$

where k is the calibration parameter.

FATIGUE METHODOLOGY

Two types of swept sinusoidal methods will be addressed next: the logarithmic and the linear sine sweeps. In a **logarithmic swept sine** signal the instantaneous number of cycles are a function of the instantaneous frequency increment (Δf_i) and the sweep constant R :

$$n_i = \frac{\Delta f_i}{R} \quad (23)$$

where

$$R = \frac{\ln(f_{\max}) - \ln(f_{\min})}{T} \quad (24)$$

And $f_{\min} / f_{\max}$ are the lowest and highest frequencies present in the frequency interval. T is the time to sweep from $f_{\min}$ to $f_{\max}$. Defining the stress-life fatigue curve as

$$N_f = \frac{C}{\sigma_a^m} \quad (25)$$

the instantaneous damage is evaluated as:

$$d_i = \frac{\Delta f_i \sigma_a^m}{R \cdot C} \tag{26}$$

which can be integrated in the frequency interval (f_{min} - f_{max}) to obtain the total damage, Lee et al. [8]:

$$d_{Total} = \sum d_i = \int_{f_{min}}^{f_{max}} \frac{\sigma_a^m}{R \cdot C} df = \frac{1}{R \cdot C} \int_{f_{min}}^{f_{max}} \sigma_a^m df \tag{27}$$

Alternatively, in the **linear swept signal** the instantaneous number of cycles are obtained by:

$$n_i = f_i \frac{\Delta f_i}{R} \tag{28}$$

where

$$R = \frac{f_{max} - f_{min}}{T} \tag{29}$$

so that the instantaneous damage can be defined as:

$$d_i = \frac{f_i \Delta f_i \sigma_a^m}{R \cdot C} \tag{30}$$

and the integration results in the total damage:

$$d_{Total} = \sum \frac{f \sigma_a^m}{R \cdot C} \Delta f = \int_{f_{min}}^{f_{max}} \frac{f \sigma_a^m}{R \cdot C} df = \frac{1}{R \cdot C} \int_{f_{min}}^{f_{max}} f \sigma_a^m df \tag{31}$$

Figure 3 illustrates the workflow for the evaluation of fatigue from a sine sweep load in the frequency domain. The blue boxes represent the inputs while the light grey boxes represent the process. Two finite element analyses are required: The modal (*or frequency extraction*) and the harmonic (*or steady state dynamic*). Combined, these two analyses result in the Stress FRF within the frequency interval, which can be scaled by a sweep profile to attend the design requirements. Next, the multiaxial reduction takes place by either CP or Von Mises approaches. The analysis setup then requires the sweep type (log or linear) and duration as well as the material SN Curve so that either Equations 27 or 31 can be used to calculate damage and life.

FIGURE 3 Sine Sweep fatigue workflow.

METHODOLOGY VERIFICATION

Figure 4 shows the finite element model chosen for the comparison between time and frequency domain methodologies. The model was created based on the dimensions provided in the paper, Benasciutti et al. [9]. The common step to both methodologies is the modal analysis. All degrees of freedom (DOF) at point A (Figure 4) are constrained apart from the Z direction, which is the direction of the load. For the purpose of the present example the beam is made of steel. The first six natural frequencies are: 15.176Hz, 63.443Hz, 77.376Hz, 165.56Hz, 167.86Hz and 233.38Hz. Figure 5 shows the first four mode shapes.

FIGURE 4 L-Beam FE Model used in the Vibration Experiments

FIGURE 5 Modal Analysis – first 4 relevant natural frequencies. The color countours represent modal stresses.

THE FREQUENCY DOMAIN APPROACH

The Modal Superposition Harmonic Analysis is setup with the an acceleration base motion, where the acceleration (Z-direction) has the amplitude of 1G sweeping from 1Hz to 500Hz. As a result the modal coordinates are obtained as shown on Figure 6. In order to retrieve the stress tensor function (across the frequency spectrum) for a given node (in the FE model), the stress tensors for each mode (from the modal analysis) must be scaled by the corresponding modal coordinate function (from the harmonic analysis) and finally all tensor functions (the contributions of every mode) are then added.

The combination of the modal stresses (shown on Table 1 below) with the modal coordinates (shown on Figure 6) results in a tensor function (3 stress components for a shell element) for the interval from 0Hz to 500Hz. This function is called Frequency Response Function (FRF). Figure 7 shows the Von Mises Stress function (Von Mises FRF) for the node named **Point-A**.

FIGURE 6 Modal Coordinates

TABLE 1 Modal Stresses (MPa) for Node indicated at Point-A in Figure 7

	Freq [Hz]	Sxx	Syy	Sxy
Mode 1	15.18	2.67E-09	1.06E-10	-8.64E-10
Mode 2	63.44	-2.05E+03	-1.95E+02	7.72E+02
Mode 3	77.38	5.06E+03	4.00E+02	-1.90E+03
Mode 4	165.56	1.72E+03	-1.90E+03	1.19E+03
Mode 5	167.86	6.54E+03	3.47E+03	-5.35E+03
Mode 6	233.38	-7.01E+02	3.62E+03	-2.87E+03
Mode 7	257.17	-5.22E+03	-5.64E+03	6.65E+03
Mode 8	369.43	-2.33E+03	-1.78E+03	3.04E+03
Mode 9	396.81	-9.74E+03	-4.03E+03	6.60E+03
Mode 10	459.81	-1.86E+04	-3.07E+03	6.91E+03

FIGURE 7 Frequency Response Function (Von Mises Stress) at Point A.

FIGURE 8 Frequency Response Function (Von Mises Stress) at Point A.

THE TIME DOMAIN APPROACH

The sine sweep (1Hz to 500Hz) can also be represented in the time domain (Figure 2). The time-domain sinusoidal load is used in the harmonic analysis with the goal of obtaining time-domain modal coordinates shown below:

FIGURE 9 Time domain modal coordinates for the first 5 relevant modes

The modal coordinates and modal stresses are combined the same way as in the frequency domain approach, resulting in stress histories like the one shown in Figure 10, for Point-A (node 48396).

FIGURE 10 Von Mises Stress for node 48396 (Point-A).

Life at Point-A is found to be 947 repeats. Using the predicted life from the time domain approach as the basis, the frequency domain approach (predicted life of 805 repeats) under-estimated the fatigue life by 15%. It is important to notice that the the frequency domain approach is always more conservative than the time domain, and the differences depend mainly on the sweep time, sweep type and damping. A broader discussion about frequency and time domain approaches is found in Morais et al. [10] and Morais [11].

1DOF CASE STUDY

A One Degree-of-Freedom (1-DOF) study was performed in order to evaluate the influence of the aforementioned parameters (sweep time, sweep type and damping) on the time and frequency domain fatigue results from a sine swept loading. Linear and log sine-swept harmonic forces excite the *SDOF* system shown on Figure 11-A.

FIGURE 11 Von Mises Stress for node 48396 (Point-A).

The excitation frequency varies from 5Hz to 100Hz within a given time T, which is the variable under investigation. The differences in the fatigue results from the frequency and time domain calculations are due to the time (or lack of) spent around the dominant resonant frequencies. The response in Figure 11-D comes from the solution of the equation of motion in the time domain. Figure 11-C corresponds to the steady state solution of the equation of motion. Figure 11-B presents the adopted *SN* Fatigue Curve.

As Figure 12 shows the longer the sweep duration the smaller the differences between time and frequency domain life results. The differences fall below 10% for both sweep times for a sweep duration higher than 600 seconds.

FIGURE 12 The influence of sweep time on the errors between frequency (*log and linear sweeps*) and time domain approaches.

As Figure 13 shows, the higher the damping (and longer the sweep time) the smaller the differences between time and frequency domain (log sweep) life results. The trend is similar for the linear sweep as illustrated in Figure 14.

FIGURE 13 Difference between frequency and log swept time as a function of damping ratio

FIGURE 14 Difference between frequency and linear swept time as a function of damping ratio

A NOTE ON RANDOM VIBRATION

It must be highlighted that the terms random and frequency domain are not always related to vibration. Sine Sweep vibration, for instance, is a deterministic vibration, not random. And both random and deterministic vibration can be approached either in the frequency or time domain. Then it must be also clarified whether random and deterministic approaches can be used interchangeably in both random and deterministic scenarios.

Consider a sinusoidal acceleration signal of constant amplitude $1.5G$ sweeping from 0.1Hz to 100Hz . Consider also a one element FE model that, under a base motion vibration from the swept frequency ($0.1\text{Hz} - 100\text{Hz}$) produces a frequency response function (through the harmonic solution) like the one shown in Figure 15 below. The largest stress is 1242.69MPa , peaking at exactly 10Hz . Regard also the fatigue SN curve as given by the expression $N = 4.92e29 \cdot S_a^{-9.82}$.

FIGURE 15 Stress Frequency Response Function caused by an acceleration base motion

From this point two types of analysis can be done: a deterministic (sine swept) fatigue analysis or random fatigue analysis. Consider a *linear sine sweep analysis* with amplitude of $0.25G$. The stress frequency response function in Figure 15 is then weighted by this sine sweep amplitude and the result is represented in the Figure 16 below.

FIGURE 16 Stress Frequency Response Function weighted by a constant amplitude sine sweep profile of $0.25G$.

The integration of the stress amplitude function in Figure 16, taking into account the fatigue curve parameters ($C = 4.92e29$ and $m = -9.82$), Equation 31 results in **Life of 9603 repeats**. These are repeats of a 1000 seconds long loading block.

A sine sweep time signal (as any other time signal) can be transformed into a PSD signal (through fast Fourier transform technique). Then the aforementioned linear sine sweep of constant amplitude of $0.25G$ turns into the acceleration PSD shown in the Figure 17 below. By looking at this PSD it is tempting to regard it as white noise, but that would be incorrect since the white noise is a random signal by definition.

FIGURE 17 Acceleration PSD that corresponds to a linear sine sweep of amplitude 0.25G.

A stress PSD is obtained after combining the FRF shown in Figure 15 and the acceleration PSD above, by means of Equation 32:

$$G_{stress}(f) = FRF(f)^T \cdot G_{acc}(f) \cdot FRF(f) \tag{32}$$

FIGURE 18 Stress PSD after combining the FRF (Figure 15) and the acceleration PSD (Figure 17)

From the stress PSD the spectral moments are calculated according to Equation 33, Morais et al. [12]:

$$m_n = \int_0^{\infty} f^n \cdot G_{stress}(f) df \tag{33}$$

The 0th and 2nd spectral moments are found to be: $m_0 = 310.06$ (RMS=17.61), $m_2 = 3.0919e4$. The number of upward zero crossings is calculated as

$$n_0^+ = \sqrt{\frac{m_2}{m_0}} = 9.9917 \tag{34}$$

Writing the *SN* equation in the following form: $S_a = 1056 \cdot N^{-0.10183}$, the fatigue parameters are the following: $k = 1056$ and $b = -0.10183$. Using the Steinberg approach, Steinberg [13]:

$$D_{STEIN} = \frac{n_0^+ T}{k^{-1/b}} \left[0.683 \left(1 \sqrt{m_0} \right)^{-1/b} + 0.271 \left(2 \sqrt{m_0} \right)^{-1/b} + 0.043 \left(3 \sqrt{m_0} \right)^{-1/b} \right] \tag{35}$$

Assuming the duration to be $T=1000$ seconds, damage is calculated as $D_{STEIN} = 8.07e-11$, and consequently life corresponds to **1.24e10 repeats** of the loading block. Dirlik’s method (Dirlik [14]) could also be used, which would result in life of **9.4e9 repeats**.

The log sine sweep is more damaging than the linear sine sweep. In the present case a logarithmic sinusoidal sweep loading would have resulted in life of **6637 repeats**, 31% lower than the linear sweep. Figure 19 shows the log sweep of the acceleration signal (constant amplitude of 0.25G) represented as a PSD. As before, a stress PSD can be obtained by combining the *FRF* in Figure 15 to the acceleration PSD in Figure 19. From the stress PSD the spectral moments can be calculated: $m_0 = 475.4$, $m_2 = 4.477e4$. Using Steinberg approach Life is evaluated as **1.562e9 repeats**, whereas by using Dirlik Life is evaluated as **1.28e9 repeats**.

FIGURE 19 Acceleration PSD that corresponds to a log sine sweep of amplitude 0.25G.

This example clearly shows the random vibration fatigue approach is not adequate to estimate life of structures subjected to swept sinusoidal loads. Dirlik and Steinberg in this case were unable to predict fatigue failure, although the proposed frequency domain sine sweep methodology is able to predict low cycle fatigue in both scenarios: linear and logarithmic sine sweeps.

It is not surprising that the random vibration fatigue approach fails to predict fatigue of swept sinusoidal loads, since such loads are not Gaussian (kurtosis=1.5 for both linear and log sweeps). It should be noted that Gaussianity, Ergodicity and Stationarity are the pre-requisites for the random vibration fatigue approach to be applicable, Thesing and Bishop [15].

SUMMARY

A new swept sine frequency domain fatigue approach has been proposed in this paper. Equations 27 and 31 are the proposed expression for fatigue damage of vibration under sinusoidal sweep loading. It is shown that the proposed approach is equivalent to the time domain approach and the difference between fatigue results from both approaches decreases with sweep time. The single DOF model shows that a sweep time longer than 600 seconds is enough to keep the differences (in fatigue results) lower than 10%. Damping always plays a crucial role in structural dynamics and in this particular case the larger the damping the smaller the differences (in fatigue results) between time and frequency domain approaches. It was also shown that the logarithmic sweep is more damaging than the linear sweep and is therefore the best choice for testing. It was demonstrated that the random vibration fatigue approach is not suitable to scenarios where the loading is a sinusoidal sweep since it doesn't comply with the Gaussianity requirement. The random vibration approach is inaccurate and non-conservative in sine sweep scenarios and consequently should not be used in those.

Contact Information

Giovanni de Morais can be contacted at Giovanni.demorais@3ds.com or giovanni@fastmail.us

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